

1 **HIV-2 infection in HEK293T.**

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7 We established and studied a cell line model of HIV-2 infection in human embryonic kidney HEK293T
8 cells. We report here EMT-like changes (i.e., *Col1a1*, *Col6a3*) specifically induced by infection with HIV-2
9 but not HIV-1 at early points in lentiviral infection. EMT-like changes were accompanied by specific
10 modulation of cytoskeletal genes, including the activity related cytoskeleton associated protein, or *ARC*.

11 Citations

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